

**Combating gender stereotypes by
highlighting women's contribution to the
history of societies**

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1. Gender equality and gender representation in Bulgaria

Gender equality aims to eliminate discrimination and bias based on gender, while at the same time challenging traditional stereotypes and gender roles, assigned by society, that have often restricted and disadvantaged individuals based on their gender throughout history. Gender equality is not just beneficial for women; it is essential for the progress and well-being of societies as a whole. It recognizes that gender should not be a determinant of a person's worth, capabilities, or potential in society.

Bulgaria is among the countries that has been making progress in the field of gender equality, but there are still significant challenges to overcome on a national level. With 60.7 out of 100 points, Bulgaria ranks 18th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index for 2022¹. Its score is 7.9 points below the EU's average score. Our desk research showed that in recent years, Bulgaria has made efforts to address gender equality in various areas such as education, employment, and political representation, however, gender disparities persist in some key areas, and traditional gender roles and stereotypes continue to influence society.

Education has played a crucial role in promoting gender equality and empowering women in the country². Women have equal access to education and are well-represented in various fields of study, including STEM. Bulgaria is even a leader among EU countries when it comes to women studying and working in ICT with, respectively, 34.4% and 27.7% of all tech-related students and employees³. Women's participation in the **labour market** is relatively high in Bulgaria. However, they often face challenges related to the gender pay gap and underrepresentation in leadership positions. Women tend to be concentrated in certain sectors, while others, particularly high-level managerial roles, remain predominantly occupied by men. The gender pay gap and workplace discrimination have also been issues that have impacted women's advancement in their careers.

Women's **representation in politics** is relatively low. Although there have been some improvements in recent years, women remain underrepresented in the parliament and other decision-making bodies. During the 45th National Assembly of Bulgaria (elected in April 2021), women accounted for approximately 26% of the total number of members. This was an improvement compared to previous years, but it still fell short of achieving gender parity. Women's underrepresentation in the political sphere can be attributed to various factors,

¹ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2022/country/BG>

² <https://ekfwomen.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/ekaterina-karavelova-report-needs-assesment-study.pdf>

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/EDN-20170426-1>

including traditional gender roles, cultural attitudes, and stereotypes, which might discourage women from pursuing political careers.

Violence against women, including domestic violence and sexual harassment, is a significant issue in Bulgaria. Despite efforts to address it through legislation and awareness campaigns, there is still a lot of work to be done to combat gender-based violence effectively. Traditional gender roles and stereotypes persist in the Bulgarian society, influencing various aspects of life, including family dynamics and career choices. These stereotypes often perpetuate gender inequalities and limit opportunities for both men and women.

2. Legislative and policy framework

A thorough review on the legislative and policy framework in the country showed that the Bulgarian Constitution of 1991 upholds the principle of equality, ensuring equal rights for all citizens regardless of various factors. The Law on Equality between Women and Men, established in 2016, emphasizes gender mainstreaming, integrating gender equality principles into legislation and policies. Additionally, the Law on Protection from Discrimination, in effect since January 2004, prohibits discrimination, including based on sex.

The National Strategy for Promoting the Equality of Women and Men 2021-2030 is a key policy document for gender equality and is implemented through annual national plans. The current action plan is the Action Plan for the Promotion of Equality Between Women and Men 2021-2022, which utilizes quantitative indicators for monitoring progress and designates specific agencies responsible for data collection⁴.

To make further progress in gender equality, Bulgaria needs to continue addressing the underlying societal norms, cultural attitudes, and institutional barriers that perpetuate gender disparities. This includes implementing and enforcing legislation that protects women's rights, promoting women's participation in decision-making processes, and challenging harmful gender norms through education and awareness campaigns. Additionally, working towards a more inclusive and equal society should involve engaging men and boys in the conversation on gender equality, as they play a vital role in transforming attitudes and behaviours.

In general, gender representation in Bulgaria, particularly in politics and leadership positions, showed some disparities. Challenges remain, and addressing them requires an **intersectional approach**⁵, including promoting women's education, challenging gender stereotypes, providing support for work-life balance, and implementing measures to promote women's representation in decision-making bodies.

⁴ <https://www.unwomen.org/en/get-involved/step-it-up/commitments/bulgaria>

⁵ https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/countries/bulgaria?language_content_entity=en

3. Gender representation in the history of Bulgaria

Women's role before the 20th century was shaped by various social, cultural, and historical factors. The status and experiences of women in this period were influenced by traditional patriarchal norms and the country's historical development. In the traditional Bulgarian society, women typically played central roles within the family and household. They were responsible for domestic duties, childcare, and nurturing the well-being of their families. Education opportunities for women were limited before the 20th century. Formal education was often reserved for boys, while girls received informal education at home, focusing on domestic skills and basic literacy. Women had limited legal and political rights. Inheritance and property rights were often biased towards male heirs, and women did not have the right to vote or participate in public affairs. Customarily, young women were expected to marry and take on the role of a wife and mother at an early age. Although traditional gender roles and societal norms placed restrictions on women's freedom of movement and social interactions, women in Sofia and other cities often engaged in various crafts and trades. They could be found working as weavers, embroiderers, traders, and more.

It's important to note that the experiences of women in Bulgaria before the 20th century were diverse and could vary significantly based on factors such as region, social class, and family circumstances. While traditional gender roles were prevalent, some women found ways to assert their agency and contribute to their communities in various capacities. Over time, social and cultural changes, along with women's movements and advocacy, have gradually led to greater gender equality and expanded opportunities for women.

In the 19th and 20th century Bulgarian women became important participants in the modernized Bulgarian society⁶. Currently, this activity and accomplishments of theirs are almost completely forgotten by the public, and even historical studies present them only as passive witnesses of the events. This is reflected in the collective memory of the nation, where female participation in the creation of national culture is minimized or even completely denied.

⁶https://www.academia.edu/27595229/%D0%A4%D0%B5%D0%BC%D0%B8%D0%BD%D0%B8%D1%81%D1%82%D0%BA%D0%B0_%D1%80%D0%B0%D0%B7%D1%85%D0%BE%D0%B4%D0%BA%D0%B0_%D0%B2_%D0%A1%D0%BE%D1%84%D0%B8%D1%8F_%D0%BA%D1%80%D0%B0%D1%87%D0%BA%D0%B0_%D0%BA%D1%8A%D0%BC_%D1%81%D1%8A%D0%B7%D0%B4%D0%B0%D0%B2%D0%B0%D0%BD%D0%B5_%D0%BD%D0%B0_herstory

4. Gender representation in the history of Sofia

In Sofia there are very few places of memory, related to the activities and accomplishments of women. In 2017 the Municipal Cultural Institute confirmed⁷ that the total number of commemorative signs (or memorial sites) on the territory of the municipality is between 600 and 700. Separately, there are 140 military monuments and 20 military monuments dedicated to foreign troops. Despite these huge numbers, the cultural institute remains unaware of any works of art dedicated to specific women as historical figures. There are 38 memorial plaques dedicated to women, though, of which no more than 30 are still preserved. They denote the homes of famous women writers and poets, artists, actresses and socialites. There are also three tombstones in public places. Unfortunately, most of these memorial locations are damaged and defiled. None of them are indicated on the geographical maps and in the tourist guides of Sofia, they were not created systematically (with a clear criteria and consistency), do not practically affect the collective activity of women (social and professional), are not targeting neither the residents of the city (due to their brevity or unfortunate placement), nor the foreign tourists (due to the lack of bilingual signs and cultural routes), are not present in the modern information environment, nor in various touristic websites.

5. Female footprint in Sofia

Sofia's history has been shaped by many remarkable women who have made significant contributions to the city, its citizens, and its development. Here are some historical female figures associated with Sofia:

- **Rayna Knyaginya** (1856-1917): a teacher, maternity nurse, and revolutionary, famous for having sewn the flag of the April Uprising of 1876, which she waved together with other freedom fighters. As the uprising was brutally crushed by Ottoman troops, she was captured, raped, molested, and beaten for more than a month in prison. While receiving education abroad, she arranged the upbringing of 32 orphans from her hometown, including her younger brother, through a ladies' charity committee.
- **Ekaterina Karavelova** (1860-1947): a well-known educator, translator, writer, publicist, suffragist, and women's rights activist. She also had an active role in protecting Bulgaria's Jewish population from deportation to concentration camps in WWII. Ekaterina was also the long-term chairwoman of the Union of Bulgarian Women Writers, created on her initiative. She represented Bulgaria at the 4th Congress of the International Women's League for Peace and Freedom in 1924 in Washington, USA. She was the founder of the cultural women's organization Maika (Mother) and its chairperson in 1899-1929. Active as a teacher, Ekaterina was early on active in the debate of women's education and status of female teachers.

⁷ <https://www.bghelsinki.org/bg/campaigns/pametni-jeni>

- **Elisaveta Bagryana** (1893-1991): a prominent Bulgarian poet who lived in Sofia for much of her life. She is considered one of Bulgaria's most significant poets, often called "the first lady of Bulgarian women's literature". Elisaveta has been nominated for the Nobel Prize in Literature three times and made substantial contributions to the country's literary heritage.
- **Yana Yazova** (1912-1974) – a writer and intellectual from 20th century. Her poetry was translated into Esperanto, Czech, Serbian and Ukrainian. She travelled extensively in Europe and the Middle East and wrote about her travels as well. Her historical novel Alexander of Macedon, the trilogy Balkans and the anti-communist novel Salt Gulf were published after her death.
- **Mara Belcheva** (1868-1937) – a poet, teacher, translator, and philologist. She published three collections of poetry: "Footsteps on the Threshold", 1918, "Sonnets", 1926, and "Selected Songs", 1931. Mara published a biography of her late partner, poet Pencho Slaveykov, in 1925. She also translated Friedrich Nietzsche's Thus Spoke Zarathustra and Gerhart Hauptmann's Die versunkene Glocke into Bulgarian.
- **Anastasia Dimitrova** (1815-1894) – the first female teacher in Bulgaria. In 1839 she founded the first Bulgarian girls' school, thus, laying the foundation of modern education in the country and conquering the place of women in education.
- **Anna Karima** (1871-1949) - writer, translator, editor and journalist, suffragist and women's rights activist. In 1897 she founded the Women's Educational Association called "Conscious" through which Anna, with her constant letters to the government, managed to convince them to allow women to study in university in 1901. Anna also founded the Bulgarian Women's Union and organized the first congress of feminist organizations. Throughout her life she's constantly engaged in translating and writing own materials, all of them focused on feminine topics – from education of children, to opposing arranged marriages, to expressing freely one's emotions – her works challenge the traditional understandings at the time, combat stereotypes and influence the attitudes of women.
- **Elena Markova-Bosilkova** (1894-1971) – the first Bulgarian female architect.
- **Teodora Peykova** (1892-1972) – a writer, editor, and socialite, she founded the lady's magazine "Economy and household", which was published by 25 years. Through the magazine Teodora spread European taste and ideas throughout the country and used it to educate women about different social issues or inventions made by other women, to offer recipes and medical advice, weight-loss diets, press review, family advice, child-rearing advice, fashion, historical events, gymnastics, reports from Paris and other cities, advertisements, courses on sewing, embroideries, needlework, etc. She also became the first Bulgarian woman who taught herself how to drive her husband's car.
- **Konstantsa Lyapcheva** (1887-1944) – socialite, involved in charity activities for unprivileged children (refugees, orphans, etc.). In the 1930s she was the first woman

to actively engage with issues such as human trafficking, domestic violence, child protection. She was the chairwoman of the Union for the Protection of Children of Bulgaria until the very end. She was a member of almost all other charitable organizations of Sofia, in many of them – as part of the management body. There is no area of social welfare in which she did not take part. Thanks to Konstanza, the activities of raising and educating children became the subject of law and received legislative protection, and motherhood was recognized as an extremely important social function. Upon her initiative, in 1927, June 1 was celebrated as Children's Day for the first time. She founded the first shelter homes for children in distress, for the training of social workers, summer camps and playgrounds.

- **Elisaveta Konsulova-Vazova** (1881-1965) – one of the first women professional artists in Bulgaria, the first Bulgarian woman to paint a nude figure at the State School of Painting and the first woman to host a solo exhibition. Elisaveta describes her revolutionary feminist ideas regarding child-rearing in a book about education – “Book for young mothers”. She is one of the founders of the Puppet Theater and the first editor-in-chief of the magazine "Home and World".
- **Elizaveta Karamihailova** (1897-1968) – the first female nuclear physicist in the country, she established the first practical courses of particle physics in Bulgaria and was the first woman to hold a professorial title in the country. Elizaveta graduated as a PhD in Physics and Mathematics in Vienna and was appointed as a docent of Experimental Atomistics with Radioactivity at Sofia University in 1939. She founded the radioactivity laboratory at the Physics Institute of the Bulgarian Science Academy.

It's important to note that some of the places, related to the women in this list, are no longer preserved or are not known in detail (with a specific location) due to the substantial lack of recorded female history. Despite their absence in history textbooks that further on creates the wrong impression that women have no contribution to the development of Bulgarian society, all these historical figures have left a lasting impact on Sofia's culture, politics, and intellectual life. Their accomplishments should continue to be remembered and celebrated in the city's history and heritage.

6. Sofia's practices in disseminating gender balanced history

The availability of information on practices to promote gender-balanced history in Sofia is limited due to the significant autonomy of various municipal administrations and entities responsible for educational and cultural initiatives. Public institutions established by municipal administrations, including libraries, museums, and cultural centers, often independently carry out small-scale initiatives to disseminate gender-balanced history. These initiatives may involve organizing exhibitions, public lectures, tours, and other activities.

Additionally, private efforts and initiatives run by different NGOs⁸ or non-formal groups have also contributed to these endeavours. Thanks to them, there has been a recent increase in exhibitions, installations, and other public media campaigns, highlighting women and their contributions to society, showcasing their work and their impact.

7. Local strategies

No public information on local strategies for promoting gender balanced history was found for the purpose of this report. Topics of “gender” or “women” are absent from the school curriculum for highschool students. These topics are also absent in municipal strategic action plans and strategic development plans.

Moreover, the term “gender” entered Bulgarian language with a negative connotation, primarily due to the targeted right-wing rhetoric against the Istanbul Convention that led to a misconception of the term for the general public. In 2018 Bulgaria became the first country that refused to ratify the document and set a dangerous precedent by its inaction towards women in risk. The topic is still relevant nowadays, especially considering the rising number of cases of gender-based violence in the country in the past years.

8. Focus Group with Young People: Summary of analyses and results

8.1. Findings on ‘Female and male historical figures’

The general observation of the focus group showed that names of male historical figures, especially man in power (kings, emperors, warriors, leaders, etc.) come to mind easily and without hesitation, as to, when it comes to women in history, the participants struggled to provide examples at first. When given more time to consider the question, they provided diverse examples, starting with women in art and literature, and going to sciences and women in power.

8.2. Findings on ‘Gender Representation’

The prevailing explanation of this focus group highlights the historical absence of political and social rights for women compared to today. This disparity is the main reason behind the extensive gender misrepresentation and the noticeable gaps in historical records and student textbooks. Participants express a sense of frustration and acknowledgement of this void, considering it unfortunate that such omissions exist. Numerous women have played significant roles in shaping their respective communities and have made valuable contributions to society. It is crucial to learn about their achievements with the same level of

⁸ <https://boulevardbulgaria.bg/articles/izlozhba-buditelkite-vazrazhda-spomena-za-15-vidni-balgarki>

respect given to men's accomplishments. Women are often portrayed from the perspective of others, predominantly men, be it their husbands or lovers. Regrettably, in most instances, scandals take precedence over other aspects of their lives.

8.3. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'

The first crucial step is to reform the education system by emphasizing the inclusion of women and their accomplishments, rather than relegating them to mere mentions as someone's wife or muse. This change is essential to ensure a more comprehensive and accurate representation of history, recognizing the significant contributions women have made throughout time.

By replacing street names with those of influential women who contributed to the development of Sofia and Bulgaria, we can address the current gap in representation. Presently, the central streets of Sofia primarily bear the names of Russian generals who played roles in the Russian-Turkish war, leading to Bulgaria's liberation, along with prominent Bulgarian figures and even foreign individuals like Joliot-Curie. Introducing the names of women who made significant contributions would be a meaningful step toward recognizing their impact on the city and the country.

Furthermore, the participants highlighted other successful methods they've faced before:

- In school, teachers organize quizzes, games, and screenings of both documentaries and live action movies that highlight the accomplishments of women. Additionally, students have the opportunity to engage with representatives from NGOs working in the field of feminism through organized meetings and discussions.
- Social media campaigns
- Online games

8.4. Findings on 'Transnational HerStory map'

The participants suggested that the map should be interactive, accessible via different platforms/systems through QR-codes. It should be able to show more content (articles, photos, and most importantly – videos) when a person reaches a specific location to learn more about the woman in question.

As for the tours, the participants gave the following recommendations:

- Traditional Guided City Tour: A classic in-person city tour led by knowledgeable guides to explore the historical landmarks and cultural treasures of the city.
- Interactive City Tour: An in-person city tour enriched with interactive elements such as treasure hunts, quizzes, and quests, making the experience more engaging and entertaining. There should be a base version of the tour where the visitor gets to walk all locations selected, and an extended version in which they get to answer quiz questions and take part in scavenger hunts, related to the women from the map.

- Self-Guided City Tour: In-person city tours can be done individually, equipped with a digital map or guide and QR codes, allowing participants to explore at their own pace while still accessing valuable information.
- Virtual City Tour: A virtual city tour designed to accommodate people with disabilities or in case of adverse weather conditions, offering an immersive digital experience that showcases the city's highlights and historical significance.

9. Focus Groups with Stakeholders: Summary of analyses and results

9.1. Findings on 'History through the lens of their expertise'

The stakeholders involved in the focus group listed the following main challenges they face when creating and presenting content about women's contributions or when discussing the topic of equality between men and women with youngsters:

- Stereotypical views of history as a male-dominated field.
- General stereotypical perceptions of women as equally capable to men in different spheres.
- Insufficient history recorded about women – as mentioned by the stakeholders, recorded history is usually the “history of power”, and since women were rarely in power through most of history, their contributions are not recorded or, if recorded, are sometimes attributed to men (the “Matilda” effect).
- Inadequate and outdated methodological resources for teachers – books that predominantly focus on male history, leaving out the movements for women rights and accomplishments by women.
- Limited commemoration of historic women figures in public places, such as through monuments or commemorative plaques – there are barely any, devoted to women in Bulgaria.

Moreover, the stakeholders discussed the difficulties in engaging a diverse audience to content, related to women's historical influence or their specific accomplishments in science, arts, etc. Such events are predominantly visited by passionate activists for gender equality but rarely attract the general public. Celebrations such as the ones for International Women's Day are among the few exceptions that lead to increased engagement with more diverse audience.

9.2. Findings on 'Experience with young people in the field of History'

The participants shared that the youngsters in Bulgaria are curious and interested in different modern topics, including gender equality and history. Those with sparked up interest may be few but they follow the topics vividly and passionately. When it comes to equality or women

representation, the numbers of interested young people increase every year, including the share of girls in entrepreneurship initiatives. More and more young women are stepping up and gaining confidence to work or study in their desired field, despite the bias and stereotypes.

All stakeholders agree that gender issues should be implemented and discussed as part of the formal curriculum to combat different stereotypes, arising in society. Currently, it's not being actively thought in school, the topic is brought up only in case the teacher is passionate about it. If fair gender representation is to be discussed with young people both in formal and informal education, it would require proper tools to make the topic more accessible to youngsters, such as:

- Games
- Quizzes
- Role plays
- Missions
- Experiential learning
- Videos, etc.

9.3. Findings on 'Women's footprint in History'

9.3.1. Representation

The stakeholders agreed that emphasis should be put on the remembrance of women across various disciplines. When seeking to recover their memory and underline their history and achievements, it is crucial to adopt an intersectional perspective, encompassing the experiences of women from different backgrounds and different occupations, such as university-educated women, literate women, freedom fighters, etc.

9.3.2. Transnational HerStory map

The map should be interactive and include challenges (missions), that, upon completion by the visitors, award them with points or some small tokens/physical stamps to collect. The app should have a long and short version, one for the very passionate tour-goers and another for the simply curious people – with and without the challenges. The participants also recommended a paper version of the map for offline tours. The map can be easily made accessible through QR-codes.

Live meetings with successful women here and now may be organized in parallel to promote the map even further and to link it to nowadays, providing context and a modern touch.

Animation works well with youngsters too. A set of videos (filmed/animated) can be released in TikTok for each of the women to highlight their stories.

Additionally, some detective games/mysteries can be created with the collected stories of women to engage youngsters.

10. Conclusions

Although our research highlights the presence of historical female figures who clearly left their mark in the city, to this day there are still no squares or monuments dedicated to them, only a few streets. In Sofia's urban space there are female images, however they always remain anonymous – the woman as a mother or as a worker, always deprived of a name, of her own history and of a contribution. The citizens of Sofia are mostly unaware of the life and accomplishments of these women, and when asked to think of historical female figures related to the city, very few names come to mind and are recognized by the general public. The suggestions provided by the participants in the focus groups represent valuable contributions on how to overcome different gender stereotypes and to highlight the history of prominent women in Sofia.